

WHAT IS POMEGRANATE USEFUL FOR

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ABSTRACT

This work is devoted to the use of pomegranates in folk medicine, as well as the chemical composition and applications.

Introduction. Pomegranate is rich in vitamins C, B6, B12, P and microelements: iodine, iron, sodium, calcium, potassium, magnesium, manganese, phosphorus. Its grains are good for the cardiovascular system and improve immunity. 100 g of pomegranate contains 70 kcal.

Pomegranate is mostly eaten fresh, but it often becomes an ingredient in various recipes. For example, its juice is often used as a marinade for meat seasoned with spices and garlic. Its grains are also added to salads, fried, stewed and boiled dishes, and made into jam. Pomegranate is universal because it goes well with many foods - vegetables, fruits, meat, poultry, etc.

Literature review. The pomegranate is quite widely reflected in the culture of the peoples who grow pomegranates - Iran, Spain (especially Granada), Azerbaijan, Armenia, Israel and others. A monument was erected to him in Iran, a stamp was issued in Romania, and a commemorative gold coin of 500 drams was minted in Armenia in 2011. On the coats of arms of some communities in France and on a significant part of the coats of arms of cities in Spain there is an image of a pomegranate. The image of a grenade on the coats of arms of the Spanish historical locality of Granada is especially characteristic.

N.I. Vavilov associates the emergence of the pomegranate culture with the Western Asian center of origin of cultivated plants, which includes inland Asia Minor, Transcaucasia, Iran and mountainous Turkmenistan. It is here that wild pomegranate thickets and the greatest diversity of cultural forms are concentrated.

Discussion. Many researchers, led by A. Decandolle, agree that the origin of the pomegranate culture should be attributed to the most distant prehistoric centuries, estimated at least 4 millennia. Botanical, historical and philological documents indicate that modern forms

of pomegranate originate from Northern Iran, Eastern Transcaucasia and Western Kopetdag. According to Hodgson[10], in the named geographical areas, pomegranate was highly revered even before the appearance of almonds, apricots and peaches in the culture. As Hodgson writes, like figs, grapes, olives, pomegranate claims one of the first places in the earliest annals of history, since in terms of its consumer value it occupied a place among primitive people along with grain crops and honey, which served as the main food of man from the first steps of civilization. Pomegranate was mentioned several times in the very early history of Greece, long before the founding of Rome, where pomegranate culture penetrated through Carthage (modern Tunisia) much later. For example, Homer mentions the pomegranate twice in the famous Odyssey as a very common fruit plant in the gardens of Phoenicia and Phrygia. The ancient Greek historian Herodotus testifies that when the Persians, under the leadership of Xerxes, attacked the Greeks, his personal guard included a special detachment, or "grenade brigade," whose soldiers carried gold garnets at the ends of their spears as the highest sign of honor. It is in the chronicle of the Battle of Marathon, which took place in 490 BC. e. The pomegranate plant was mentioned for the first time.

Theophrastus gave a very detailed description of the pomegranate in his History of Plants, written 350 BC. e. The cultivated pomegranate plant is mentioned several times in the Old Testament. According to legend, the Israelites, wandering for a long time in the desert and suffering from thirst, first became acquainted with pomegranate and its fruits in Egypt. Under King Solomon, pomegranate gardens were very popular and were sung in special songs.

In Spain, the pomegranate took root well, flourished and even became a symbol of the golden age of Granada. Modern widespread cultivated plantings of pomegranate in Spain represent one of the clearest traces of the presence of Moorish tribes in this territory. Abu al-Awwam, who lived in the 12th century, described 11 varieties of pomegranate that were common at that time in Spain. It is not without reason that Granada in Spain owes its name to the widespread fame of its pomegranate varieties, which have reached a high degree of perfection in this favorable geographical region.

To the east of the center of origin of the culture and the adjacent countries, pomegranate, apparently, moved much later than to the Mediterranean countries. In the 16th-17th centuries, pomegranate penetrated into the countries of the New World: Central, South and North America, as well as in the Old World - into South and Southeast Africa, Australia, the islands of the Indian and Pacific Oceans.

The history of pomegranate culture on the territory of the states of the former USSR is closely connected with the very first steps of agriculture in Transcaucasia. Among the states of Central Asia, the most interesting area of diversity of wild fruit plants, including pomegranate, is the territory of Turkmenistan with the western part of the Kopetdag.

Ready-made cultural forms from Iran, Turkmenistan and partly Northern Afghanistan penetrated into Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. N.I. Vavilov[11], characterizing the pomegranate culture in Afghanistan, where he was on an expedition.

B. S. Rozanov[6] came to the conclusion that the pomegranate culture in the Central Asian states dates back at least 2 thousand years, and possibly much more. This conclusion is possible thanks to some archaeological finds obtained, in particular, by the expedition of S.P. Tolstov[12] during the excavations of the Khorezm castle of Toprak-Kala, the existence of which dates back

to the beginning of the 4th century. In the remains of wall paintings of the castle, an image of the fertility goddess Anahita with fruits in her hand was discovered.

Garnets were used in the Czech Republic and Slovakia back in the Bronze Age, in Egypt more than 5 thousand years ago, in Sumer two thousand years BC, and also in Sweden between the second and first millennia BC. Garnets were very popular in ancient Greek and ancient Roman civilizations. According to legend, the garnet was one of the twelve stones in the breastplate of the high priest and was used as a sacred stone among American Indians and African tribes.

Chemical composition. The bark of roots, trunks and branches contains alkaloids pseudopeltierine, methylisopelletierine, isopelletierine (30-40%), betulinic acid; ursolic acid (0.6%) was found in the peel; in leaves it is 0.45%. The bark of the trunks and the rind of the fruits, in addition, contain up to 28% tannins, the fruits contain vitamin C, and the flowers contain punicin. The fruit rind also contains:

macronutrients (mg/g) K-18,9, Ca-4,0, Mg-0,5, Fe-0,05;
microelements (mkg/g) – Mn – 5,28, Cu – 2,5, Zn – 3,8, Mo – 0,4, Cr – 0,32,
Al-33,68, Se –0,08, Ni –0,32, Sr –19,36, B –54,4

Application The fruits are rich in sugars, tannins, and vitamin C. Pomegranate juice is considered useful for anemia; A decoction of the peel and membranous partitions is used as an astringent for burns and indigestion (due to the high content of tannins). The sour reddish pulp of pomegranate is used in desserts and salads, as well as for making soft drinks. In Armenia, pomegranate is used to prepare blended dessert and fortified wines.

Вывод. Гранат усиливает внутренний огонь, чтобы привести творческие замыслы к их реализации. Он является мощным камнем активации и регенерации, укрепляет, уравнивает и защищает своего владельца. Камень выводит токсины из тела, очищает жизненно важные органы и кровь, помогает в усвоении витаминов и минералов. Гранат уравнивает энергию, исцеляет от меланхолии и депрессии, укрепляет инстинкт выживания и привлекает смелость и надежду в критических ситуациях. Он считается счастливым камнем для любви, успеха и деловых отношений, помогает отпустить старые модели поведения и повышает уверенность в себе. Гранаты превосходны в борьбе с плохими снами и депрессивными состояниями ума (для этого гранат надо положить на ночь под подушку). Этот кристалл регенерирует клетки тела, влияет на позвоночник, очищает кровь, сердце и лёгкие, восстанавливает ДНК. По мнению литотерапевтов, он облегчает ревматические боли и боли в суставах, лечит некоторые психические заболевания. Энергия камня приносит успех и в любви, и в деловых отношениях, в бизнесе (для бизнес-целей идеально подходит гранат, огранённый в форму квадрата или прямоугольника).

Conclusion. Garnet enhances inner fire to bring creative ideas to fruition. It is a powerful stone of activation and regeneration, strengthening, balancing and protecting its owner. The stone removes toxins from the body, cleanses vital organs and blood, and helps in the absorption of vitamins and minerals. Garnet balances energy, heals melancholy and depression, strengthens the survival instinct and attracts courage and hope in critical situations. Considered a lucky stone for love, success and business relationships, it helps to let go of old patterns and increases self-confidence. Garnets are excellent in the fight against bad dreams

and depressive states of mind (for this, a garnet should be placed under the pillow at night). This crystal regenerates body cells, affects the spine, cleanses the blood, heart and lungs, and restores DNA. According to lithotherapists, it relieves rheumatic pain and joint pain, and treats some mental illnesses. The energy of the stone brings success both in love and in business relationships, in business (a garnet cut into a square or rectangle is ideal for business purposes).

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